

A novel assay of cycloserine from capsules using 4-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde

M. G. H. Laghari*, Y. Darwis and A. H. Memon

School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 11800, Penang, Malaysia

E-mail : fairy_rose25@yahoo.com

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Abstract : A novel spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of cycloserine (CS) in capsules by derivatization with 4-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (DAC) to form CS-DAC derivative. The molar absorptivity of pure CS was calculated as 1.2×10^3 L/mole/cm at λ_{\max} 288 nm and obeyed the Beer's law within 4–20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, whereas CS-DAC derivative showed molar absorptivity of 5.8×10^3 L/mole/cm at λ_{\max} 334 nm and obeyed the Beer's law within 2–10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The reaction was highly stable up to 24 h.

The method was successfully applied for the determination of CS from various capsules. Developed method is simple, rapid, cost effective and more sensitive from already reported method for the determination of CS from pharmaceutical preparations.

Keywords : Cycloserine, 4-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Mycobacterium tuberculosis bacilli (TB) is as old as humankind and still one of the most widespread and lethal diseases. Being the most prevalent infections of human beings, it remains one of the main threats to mankind. Despite the availability of a cheap and effective treatment, tuberculosis still accounts for millions of cases of active disease and deaths worldwide and not possible to be controlled without an effective treatment/vaccination strategy, which is still a challenge to date¹. TB patients need long term therapy which may cause drug resistance to first line agent and other severe complications like anemia, inflammation, pain, liver damage and sometime crystalluria². Many drugs like isoniazid, ethambutol, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and cycloserine are used to treat TB patients³. Cycloserine chemically known as D-4-amino-3-isoxazolidone⁴ is used as an antibiotic in pulmonary tuberculosis and also enhances the treatment effects of exposure therapy in social anxiety disorder^{5,6}. CS is analyzed by various methods such as GC⁷, HPLC^{8–11}, spectrophotometric^{12–14}, fluorimetric^{15–17}, titrimetric¹⁸, biological assay^{19,20} and molecular cloning^{21,22} techniques. In the present work 4-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (DAC) is examined for the first time as a derivatizing reagent for the spectrophotometric determi-

nation of CS in capsules. El-Sayed *et al.* (1986) used *p*-benzoquinone as complexing reagent. A fluorescent compound was obtained with absorption at 381 nm. The complex has an apparent molar absorptivity of 4.76×10^3 L/mole/cm and Beer's law is obeyed over the range 4–20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. While the developed method is applied for the determination of CS by reacting with DAC reagent with improved molar absorptivity of 5.8×10^3 L/mole/cm at λ_{\max} 334 and obeyed Beer's law within 2–10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ from capsules. The aim of the present work was to develop and validate new sensitive and specific method for the determination of CS by derivatization using DAC reagent. The CS-DAC derivative was used for quantification of CS content in capsule preparation.

Results and discussion

The amino group of cycloserine (CS) reacts with the carbonyl group of *p*-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (DAC) to form Schiff's base 4-[3-(4-dimethylamino-phenyl)-allylideneamino]-isoxazolidin-3-one or CS-DAC derivative (Fig. 1) which absorbs maximally at 334 nm with bathochromic shift having molar absorptivity 5.8×10^3 L/mole/cm. DAC was therefore examined as a derivatizing reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of CS. The amount of DAC added, effects of pH, heating time

Fig. 1. Formation of CS-DAC derivative using ρ -dimethylamino-cinnam-aldehyde as a derivatizing reagent.

and temperature on the formation of (CS-DAC) derivative along with stability were studied. A linear calibration curve was obtained which obeyed the Beer's law within the concentration range 2–10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of CS-DAC derivative with coefficient of determination R^2 0.9992 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Calibration plots of CS and CS-DAC.

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for the derivatization method was calculated using the following equations²³. $LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma/S$, LOQ

$= 10 \times \sigma/S$. Where σ is the standard deviation of n replicate determinations ($n=10$) under the same conditions as for the sample analysis in the absence of the analyte, and S is the sensitivity (the slope of the calibration graph). The method was applied to determine the amount of CS quantitatively in the two capsule samples obtained from the local market (Table 1). The mean values (g) and relative error % at (99% confidence limit) was $249.1 \pm 0.777\%$, respectively (Table 2).

Table 1. Analysis of CS from (0.25 g) capsules

Drug	Amount found g/capsule (\pm % RSD)	% Relative deviations from labeled values	% Recovery using standard addition technique
Cyclokox	0.24 (1.3)	0.8	99.46
Cycloserine	0.23 (1.1)	3.6	99.86

Table 2. Regression and analytical parameters

Parameter(s)	Values
Wave length λ_{max} (nm) of CS	288
Wave length λ_{max} (nm) of CS-DAC derivative	334
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of CS	4–20
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of CS-DAC derivative	2–10
Molar absorptivity (L/mole/cm) of CS	1.2×10^3
Molar absorptivity (L/mole/cm) of CS-DAC derivative	5.8×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity of CS-DAC (Conc. at 0.004 absorbance unit $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.03
Limit of detection (LOD $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.4
Limit of quantification (LOQ $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.3
Regression equation (y/a)	
Slope (b)	0.0565
Intercept (a)	0
Coefficient of determination (R^2)	0.999
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.23–0.61
Relative deviation (\pm %)	0.136–0.53
Mean value g/capsule \pm range of error % at (99% confidence limit) of two brands	$0.249 \pm 0.777\%$

Optimization of method :

Some variables such as reagent concentration, wavelength, order of mixing, reaction time and temperature, solvents, buffers and acid concentration which affect the absorbance of the Schiff's base derivative was optimized to achieve maximum analytical sensitivity and devotion to Beer's law.

DAC reagent concentration :

The effect of different volume (0.5–2 ml) of DAC reagent (4 g/L) was observed on absorbance of CS-DAC derivative at selected wavelength (334 nm). The results showed that 1 ml of (4 g/L) DAC solution was optimum for the production of CS-DAC derivative (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Effect of volume of (4 g/L) methanolic DAC reagent on the formation of CS-DAC derivative.

Optimum wavelength :

The absorbance of pure CS and CS-DAC derivative was measured at different wavelengths between 200–500 nm. The maximum absorbance value of pure CS was obtained at 288 nm and obeyed the Beer’s law within 4–20 µg/ml whereas CS-DAC derivative showed maximum absorbance at 334 nm and also obeyed the Beer’s law within 2–10 µg/ml. So, λ 288 nm for pure CS and λ 334 nm for CS-DAC derivative were selected as optimum wavelengths (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of CS and CS-DAC derivative on different wavelength.

Addition of DAC :

The order of adding the DAC reagent during

derivatization process affected the absorbance of CS-DAC derivative. The maximum absorbance value was achieved when 1 ml of DAC (4 g/L) was added to the standard solution of CS followed by 0.5 ml of 5 N (HCl). In contrast addition of 0.5 ml of 5 N (HCl) to 10 µg of CS solution (0.5 ml) and followed by 1 ml DAC reagent (4 g/L) resulted in a decrease in absorbance value. Furthermore, adding 5 N (HCl) to the DAC reagent and followed by CS solution also gave lower absorbance value.

Reaction time and temperature :

The time and temperature for optimum reaction was determined by measuring the absorbance of CS-DAC derivative upon the addition of DAC reagent to the CS solution at various temperatures 25–60 °C for 0–40 min. The reaction was found to be quantitatively completed when the mixture was kept to stand for 30 min at room temperature (25 °C) and further delay had no consequence on the reaction in terms of absorbance measurements of CS-DAC derivative. The azomethine derivative of CS with DAC which was used for quantitation of the CS, was found to be stable up to 24 h at room temperature (25 °C).

Solvents :

The effect of different solvents to prepare CS solution was restricted to inorganic solvents because of insolubility of CS, since its solubility is limited to water and few organic solvents such as methanol, ethyl acetate and ethanol. Although CS is freely soluble in water and alcohols but the alcoholic solutions of CS cannot be used in proposed method because of instability of CS in alcoholic solution. So aqueous solution of CS was prepared which shows the negligible effect on the formation of derivative of CS with DAC. In order to select the suitable solvent for preparation of DAC solution, different solvents such as water, ethanol, methanol, acetonitrile, ethylacetate, chloroform and tetrahydrofuran were examined. DAC was insoluble in water. The reaction of CS with DAC was examined in above solvents and absorbance was measured at selected wavelength against reagent blank. It was observed that corresponding blank in alcohols and ethyl acetate gave maximum absorbance against alcoholic and ethyl acetate solution of DAC. But, methanol was proved as better solvent in terms of stability of the CS-DAC derivative (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Effect of solvents on absorbance of CS-DAC derivative.

Buffers and HCl concentration :

Very poor effect was observed on the formation of CS-DAC derivative after adding 0.5–1 ml of 0.1 M buffer solutions (pH 1–10) of hydrochloric acid, potassium chloride, acetic acid, sodium acetate, sodium bicarbonate, sodium carbonate and ammonium chloride. The effect of adding 0.5 ml of HCl concentration ranging from 1–6 N on the absorbance of 6 µg/ml CS-DAC solution at optimized conditions was therefore studied. It was observed that the absorbance increased gradually from 1 N (HCl) and was maximum at 5 N. Increasing the concentration of HCl above 5 N caused a decrease in absorbance of CS-DAC derivative. So, 5 N (HCl) was selected as optimum concentration for the derivatization of CS with DAC.

Method validation :

Linearity : The standard calibration curve for CS-DAC derivative was obtained by plotting absorbance versus concentration at the optimum experimental conditions as described in section derivatization of CS with DAC for CS-DAC derivative. The linear regression equation was obtained by the method of Beer's law range. Molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity, correlation coefficient, relative standard deviation, limits of detection and quantification for developed method are summarized in Table 2.

Accuracy and precision : In order to examine the precision of the derivatization method, two different solutions (4 µg/ml) of CS and CS-DAC derivative were prepared and analyzed in 3 replicates on the same day (intraday precision) and three consecutive days (interday precision). The low values of the % relative standard

deviation (RSD) $\leq 1.3\%$ for intraday and $\leq 2.8\%$ for interday indicate the high precision of the proposed methods. Also, the accuracy of the proposed methods was examined by % relative error (RE) $\leq 2.5\%$, which proves that proposed method has good accuracy (Table 3).

Table 3. Accuracy and precision

Day	Absorbance (\pm % RSD)	% RE
Interday	0.23 (1.3)	-1
Intraday	0.26 (2.8)	2

Specificity : Specificity of the method was evaluated by using placebo sample containing the commonly employed excipients such as mannitol, sorbitol, lactose, sucrose, glucose, galactose and fructose. The quantity of excipients was 10 times higher than CS. It was observed that none of these substances interfered with any variation in absorbance of CS-DAC derivative within $\pm 3\%$.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

Double beam spectrophotometer (UV/Visible spectrometer Lambda 25, Perkin-Elmer, USA) with dual silica 1 cm cuvettes was used for absorbance measurements. The spectrophotometer was controlled by computer with UV WinLab 25 software. The pH of various buffers was monitored by using pH meter (Schot Instrument Lab 850, Germany).

Materials :

All the reagents and chemicals of analytical grade were used. Pure cycloserine (CS), ρ -dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (DAC), acetic acid and sodium acetate were purchased from Fluka (Switzerland) and ethanol was obtained from BDH (UK). Hydrochloric acid, potassium chloride, acetic acid, sodium acetate, sodium bicarbonate, sodium carbonate and ammonium chloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

Assay of CS before derivatization :

The molar absorptivity 1.2×10^3 L/mole/cm of pure CS was observed at 288 nm by measuring the aqueous solution of CS at 200–500 nm against water. The solutions (0.2–1 ml) containing CS (20–100 µg) were trans-

ferred to 5 ml calibrated stopper volumetric flasks and the volumes were adjusted to mark with water.

Derivatization of CS with DAC :

The aqueous aliquots (0.1–0.5 ml) containing CS (10–50 µg) was transferred to 5 ml calibrated stopper volumetric flasks and 1 ml of DAC (4 g/L) was added followed by 0.5 ml of 5 N (HCl) solution. The solution in each flask was mixed and kept aside at room temperature (25 °C) for 30 min and the volume was adjusted to mark with methanol. The absorbance was measured at 334 nm against blank solution. The blank solution was prepared in a similar way without addition of CS.

Assay of CS in capsule :

Ten capsules of each pharmaceutical brand namely Cycloserine (Century Pharmaceutical (Pvt.) Ltd., Karachi, Pakistan) and Cyclokox (Radicura Pharmaceuticals (Pvt.) Ltd., New Delhi, India) were collected from market. Each capsule from both manufacturers was claimed to contain 250 mg of CS. The content of ten capsules of both brands was weighed. Accurate quantity equivalent to 10 mg of CS was transferred into a 100 ml calibrated flask and dissolved in 20 ml water then followed by the addition of 80 ml of water. The solution was stirred using magnetic stirrer for about 20 min and filtered using a Whatman No. 42 filter paper. A stock solution (1000 µg/ml) CS was diluted to get the working concentration of (100 µg/ml) CS for analysis by proposed method as described in section derivatization of CS with DAC.

Method validation :

CS powder (100 mg) was dissolved in water and the volume was adjusted to 100 ml. Two portions, each consisting of 0.3 ml of CS solution were taken in two different 5 ml volumetric flasks. One was added 0.2 ml of CS solution. The derivatization procedure was followed for both solutions as described in section derivatization of CS with DAC. The validity of the developed method was assayed using standard addition technique and % recoveries were calculated using following equation : % recovery = (collected mass/initial mass) × 100.

Conclusions

The developed method is simple, accurate, precise, inexpensive and less time consuming. The CS-DAC derivative had higher UV absorbance and molar absorptivity compared to UV underivatized CS. Furthermore, the developed method showed no interference from the formulation excipients which may absorb in the UV region of CS-DAC derivative. The method was successfully applied for the quantification of CS contents in the pharmaceutical preparations.

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